

Social Distancing Wristband Wearables

The entire world remains in dilemma due to the persistent COVID-19 pandemic, and contact tracing is extremely needed if we are likely to work against it. Distance sensors and Real-Time Location Providers (RTLS) have been revealed to be exceptionally effective tools for keeping and also observing social distancing, call mapping, handwashing, and also the room in between employees in any sector. MOKO Smart has established a series of Social Distancing Wristband Wearables items to help people in the battle against Covid-19. MOKO created these to ensure that any kind of sector can take advantage of these items for making sure safety and security in the office, as well as the capacity to track essential clients in hospitals.

Social Distancing/ Vibration Alert

Our products give you real-time signals for social distancing. When a person with a MOKO Wristband breaks the company-set security procedures and does not appreciate the WHO-recommended physical range of 6 feet (2 meters), the wristband shakes. In this circumstance, you will certainly have the ability to care for on your own in various scenarios. This will certainly help both parties, informing people if they come as well near a defined distance by a shaking alert, which will certainly lower infection danger in public or functioning areas.

Call Tracing Solutions

These products will significantly aid both individuals as well as organizations in performing call tracing for at-risk Coronavirus individuals. The MOKO Contact Tracing Wristband will find any other bands within the suggested social distancing standards of 6 feet (2 meters). Additionally, this documents the tracking information of people putting on the moko social distancing wristband, with the ID data uploaded (personal privacy secured).

Personnel Area Tracking

These items utilize the abilities of modern indoor GENERAL PRACTITIONER tracking options and IoT technologies for tracking the place of individuals who might have been subjected to the virus at one point or another. The movements of quarantined people or individuals could be surveilled to understand their real-time locations, and also the information could be made use of to intervene before the virus can spread, helping the authorities in executing any type of quarantine or monitoring plan. Leaving a

quarantine location would be signaled by vibration, which data would be reported to authorities instantaneously.

[MOKOSMART social distancing wristband](#) are a trusted tool for today's challenges of fighting the COVID-19 pandemic. Tracking solutions such as these assist companies in their goal to maintain the safety and security of their employees, by keeping an eye on movements and also carrying out dimensions to ensure safe social distancing practices. Likewise, they can identify as well as videotape violations, helping protect against COVID-19 transmission before it can begin. Finally, the wristbands' vibrations allow employees to understand when they're going against appropriate social distancing standards, which helps them in their quest for a safe, healthy work area, which can aid the whole business to remain functioning at the greatest possible level.